
103. Stellar rotation... for 3 million stars

ALL CELESTIAL BODIES rotate... galaxies, stars, and planets amongst them. The rotation of individual stars is inherited from the angular momentum of the gas and dust out of which they formed (albeit subsequently modified by various evolutionary processes), itself ultimately attributed to quantum density fluctuations in the early rapidly expanding Universe.

Since stars are fluid objects, they are neither perfect spheres, nor do they rotate as solid bodies. Instead, their rotation produces an equatorial bulge due to centrifugal forces, and generally involves differential rotation in which the angular velocity is a function of latitude. Differential rotation is believed to have a significant role in the generation of a star's magnetic field, which then interacts with the stellar wind, a process gradually slowing the star's rotation rate over its lifetime.

As a result of these and other processes, rotation is an important quantity in understanding many fundamental stellar properties, including the origin and evolution of a star's angular momentum, the role of rotation in the creation and persistence of stellar magnetic fields, magnetic braking, and in the mixing of chemical elements deep within their interiors.

Rotation also provides the basic ingredient for age determination based on gyrochronology, which exploits the star's gradual angular momentum loss over time.

THERE ARE TWO principal approaches by which stellar rotational velocities can be determined: either from its effect on the spectrum of the star, or by timing the motion of active features on the stellar surface.

The former exploits the fact that different regions of the star are moving at systematically different line-of-sight velocities, which leads to broadening of its absorption lines. From this broadening (which is further modified by effects such as microturbulence) the star's projected rotation velocity can be determined.

The latter exploits the rotational modulation of active surface features, in particular star spots and faculae. This can result in significant photometric modulation at the rotation period, recognisable if the star is monitored by accurate photometry over long periods of time.

TO PROVIDE some indicative numbers, our Sun rotates with a period of 25.05 days at the equator (1.997 km s^{-1}), and 34.4 days at its poles, and has an oblateness ($b/a - 1$) $\sim 8 \times 10^{-6}$. Extremely rapid rotating stars include Regulus (α Leo A), with a projected rotational velocity of 317 km s^{-1} , a rotation period of 15.9 h (86% of the break-up velocity), and an oblateness of 0.32. Other rapidly rotating stars include Vega and Achernar.

At the other extreme, KIC-11145123, with a rotation period of 100 d, has been claimed as the 'roundest' object in Nature, with an inferred difference of just 3 km between its polar and equatorial radii (Gizon et al., 2016).

THE STUDY of stellar rotation has been transformed within the past decade. The compilation of Glebocki et al. (2000), derived primarily from spectral line-broadening, contained just 11 000 stars of all spectral types and luminosity classes, albeit restricted to a few nearby open clusters and a few thousand bright stars.

The Kepler mission (2009–18) provided a substantial advance by characterising photometric modulation due to surface star spots and faculae. Amongst its 133 000 main-sequence targets, the combination of high photometric precision and densely-sampled long-duration observations resulted in some 34 000 rotational periods in the range 0.2–70 days (McQuillan et al., 2014). A further 30 000 were similarly identified from the extended Kepler K2 mission (Reinhold & Hekker, 2020).

This vast bounty of rotational periods from Kepler has had a profound scientific impact, ranging from advances in the understanding of star spots and faculae, of differential rotation, of gyrochronology and the effects of magnetic braking, of the consequences for asteroseismology and, for planet-hosting stars, of the effects of tidal interactions and stellar obliquities.

Interpretation of the Kepler (and other) rotation data has also been substantially augmented by Gaia astrometry. Examples include quantifying the unexplained bimodal period distribution found for field M dwarfs (Davenport & Covey, 2018); and providing an updated view of stellar rotation as a function of mass and age in nearby open clusters (Godoy-Rivera et al., 2021).

IN ADDITION to its role in aiding interpretation of stellar rotation through its astrometric distances, Gaia is also determining new rotation periods. It is able to characterise rotation using these two distinct methods: rotational modulation (using its accurate photometry) and spectral line broadening (using its RVS spectrometer data). And, for both, doing so in even larger numbers.

ALTHOUGH GAIA'S light curves are not as densely sampled in time as Kepler, the same principles of detection apply. Gaia's advantages include 3-colour time-series space photometry (G , G_{BP} , G_{RP}) covering the whole sky, and to much fainter magnitudes, $G \sim 21$.

In their study of the first 22 months of mission data in Gaia DR2, Lanzafame et al. (2018) started with the 500 000 stars already classified as variable, and identified nearly 150 000 rotation periods (and modulation amplitudes) in stars where the flux modulation is induced by surface inhomogeneities (viz. star spots and faculae).

Candidate stars, which they term BY Dra variables, embrace dwarfs (with amplitudes of milli-mag), sub-giants, and T Tauri stars (with amplitudes up to several tenths of mag). They occupy the region of the M_G versus $G_{BP} - G_{RP}$ diagram shown in colour here. Again, this will open new possibilities for understanding the evolution of angular momentum and dynamo action.

AN UPDATED version of the same pipeline has been applied to solar-like variable stars in Gaia DR3 by Distefano et al. (2022). They started with 474 000 stars with variability attributed to magnetic activity. Of these, some 430 000 are newly discovered variables, and some 150 000 have rotation periods below 1 day, i.e. fast rotators poorly sampled by previous surveys.

Some 150 000 resulted in a 'well-defined' rotation period, meaning that the period was consistent over restricted data segments, even though the total time-series loses its overall coherence, as illustrated here for their object Gaia DR3 6503897945888972544.

THE NUMBERS GET even bigger with the results from the Radial Velocity Spectrometer (RVS) spectra, which cover the wavelength range 846–870 nm. As described in Essay #87, Gaia DR3 (June 2022), contains radial velocities for 33 million stars with effective temperatures between 3100–14 500 K, and $G_{RVS} < 12$ mag.

In brief, these radial velocities are based on a comparison of the observed RVS spectrum with a library of synthetic spectral models covering a range of temperature, gravity, metallicity and reddening (and 'broadened' to match Gaia's along-scan line-spread function, due to the contribution of its optics, the detector, and the satellite spin rate).

Various physical effects intrinsic to the star can also contribute to broadening of the spectral lines (related to quantum mechanics, particle interaction, and velocity fields on scales shorter than the photon mean free path). In most cases, their spectral impact is sufficiently well described by classical atmospheric modelling, and the spectral line shapes can usually be well replicated by keeping the effective temperature, surface gravity, metallicity, and microturbulence fixed.

Ignoring the origin of such second-order effects, the DR3 pipeline also determines an *additional* line-broadening contribution ('vbroad'), assumed due exclusively to axial rotation, to best fit the observed spectra.

Details of this additional line-broadening term are discussed by Frémat et al. (2022). The resulting numbers are spectacular: the DR3 line-broadening catalogue contains 3 524 677 stars with T_{eff} ranging from 3500–14 500 K, and $G_{RVS} < 12$. And they found reasonable agreement between the DR3 values and those in other catalogue catalogues, including GALAH, APOGEE, and LAMOST.

The DR3 line-broadening catalogue represents, by far, the largest stellar sample for the determination and interpretation of stellar rotation across the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram. Their Figure 16 (above) shows the median amplitude of the line-broadening term (left) and its corresponding number density (right) across the Gaia colour–magnitude diagram.